

POTENTIAL REVERSIBILITY OF 'JOSHI EFFECT' IN IODINE VAPOUR UNDER SILENT ELECTRIC DISCHARGE

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The hysteresis in Joshi effect in I_2 observed by previous workers has been studied under different conditions of ageing and it has been observed that the phenomenon is almost entirely due to the ageing effect, and hysteresis, if any, is negligible.

Results obtained using both a diode and an IN 34 germanium crystal detector are identical and lead to the same conclusion that true hysteresis is absent.

Studies in Joshi effect, an (almost) instantaneous and reversible photo-diminution of the electrical conductivity, in iodine vapour (Deshmukh, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1949, 24A, 243; Joshi and Deshmukh, *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1942, A, 38) have shown interesting behaviour. The magnitude of the effect was observed to vary in the order: $Cl_2 > Br_2 > I_2$ (Joshi, *Cur. Sci.*, 1947, 16, 19) and in iodine vapour very little effect could be observed. The observation of Joshi effect in iodine was considered to be nearly impossible without a sensitive indicator and adequate irradiation. A time-variation of discharge current produced under a constant field, known as 'ageing', was found very prominent in iodine (Joshi and Deshmukh, *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1942, *Chem. Sec.*, Abs. No. 7) and the non-coincidence of observation for Joshi effect for rising and falling potentials, called 'hysteresis', was also recorded (Joshi and Murty, *ibid.*, 1942, *Chem. Sec.*, Abs. No. 67; Joshi and Raghavan, *ibid.*, Abs. No. 64). The light effect in iodine was reported to be both positive and negative (Joshi and Bhatt, *ibid.*, 1942, Abs. No. 61) depending upon the conditions and magnitude of applied potential. Hence, it was of interest to work out further details on iodine vapour and certain illuminating observations were recorded by the author.

EXPERIMENTAL

The general assemblage of the apparatus is similar to what has been used by various workers in the field and is shown in Figs. 1 and 2. Fig. 1 refers to when the detector used is a reflection galvanometer suitably shunted (Gambrell make) actuated by a diode 83 V (Sylvania). Fig. 2 refers to the arrangement when the detector was the same galvanometer suitably shunted and actuated by germanium crystal diode IN 34 (Sylvania). The diode is a post-war development of Sylvania Electric Company. It is reported to have a uniform rectification characteristic for various frequencies from 0 to 150 mega-cycles. For taking observations at various temperatures, a heating chamber has been introduced in which the ozoniser is kept. The chamber consists of an asbestos-lined wooden box which has a glass window on one side. The interior of the box is heated electrically by passing current through heating coils, which are distributed throughout the area to ensure uniform temperature in the enclosure. By suitably adjusting the current, the temperature could be controlled $\pm 0.2^\circ$. The temperature was varied in the heating chamber by passing different currents through the

heating coils. Half a dozen observations by varying the temperature from 23° to 100° and also by changing the chokes were taken, but only a few relevant observations have been produced.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

The ozoniser used is a Siemens type (glass) ozoniser, containing powdered iodine (Mercks' extra pure) in the bulb and connected to a Töpler for evacuation. The ozoniser was sealed off after keeping exposed for vacuum for more than 48 hours. The iodine

vapour was in contact with the solid phase. The ozoniser was in use for a pretty long time and hence it was already sufficiently "aged" when the author started work.

The ozoniser was excited under various applied fields of 90 cycles frequency and the discharge current was observed when the ozoniser was in the dark (i_d) and when irradiated (i_L) externally from an incandescent bulb placed inside a chamber with pully operated shutters. From these data, the net Joshi effect $\Delta i = i_d - i_L$ and % Joshi effect $\% \Delta i = \frac{\Delta i}{i_d} \times 100$ were calculated.

Potential variation of 'Joshi effect' in Iodine Vapour contained in an aged ozoniser

Transformer ratio = 1 : 50 app. Frequency of A. C. supply = 50 cycles/sec.
 Source of irradiation = 220 volts, 100 watt (glass) bulb. Detector = Diode 83 V.
 Temp. = 25°

TABLE I

Applied potential in kV.	Ozoniser aged for 2 hours at 5 kV (r. m. s.) Rising and falling potentials				Ozoniser aged for 8 hours at 5 kV (r. m. s.) Rising and falling potentials			
	i_d	i_L	Δi	% Δi	i_d	i_L	Δi	% Δi
0.35	4	0.5	3.5	87.5	3.25	0.5	2.75	84.6
0.4	3.5	0.5	3	85.6	2.75	0.75	2	73
0.55	2	0.5	1.5	75.	2.5	1	1.5	60.0
0.75	3.5	2.75	0.75	21.4	3.25	2.75	0.5	15
1.25	↓ 10.25	10.25	0	0	10.25	10.25	0	0

TABLE II

(a) Ozoniser aged for 1 hour at 5 kV, and left to stand.

Applied potential in kV.	Observations after 24 hours				Observations after 48 hours of the previous set.			
	i_d	i_L	Δi	% Δi	i_d	i_L	Δi	% Δi
0.35	12.2	2.75	9.5	78	12.75	2	10.75	83
0.4	15	0.75	14.25	95	13.25	0.75	12.5	94
0.55	6	1	5	83	5.5	1.25	4.25	77
0.75	5	2	3	60	4.5	2	2.5	56
1.25	↓ 9	9	0	0	↓ 10.25	10	0.25	2

(b) Ozoniser aged for 2 hours at 5 kV, and left to stand.

Observations just after.				Observations after 48 hours. p.:				
i_d	i_L	Δi	% Δi	i_d	i_L	Δi	% Δi	
0.35	4	0.5	3.5	88	11.25	0.75	10.5	93
0.4	3.5	0.5	3	86	11.75	0.5	11.25	96
0.55	2	0.5	1.5	75	3.25	0.75	2.5	77
0.75	3.5	2.75	0.75	21	3.25	2.25	1	31
1.25	↓ 10.25	10.25	0	0	↓ 10	10	0	0

TABLE III

Transformer ratio = 1 : 50 app. Frequency of A. C. supply = 50 cycles/sec. Source of irradiation = 220 volts, 100 watt (glass) bulb. Detector = IN 34 germanium crystal diode.

(a) Temp. 23°. Observations after ageing the ozoniser for a few hours.

Applied potential	Choke A = 2.5 milli henries								Applied potential	Choke B = 100 milli henries							
	Rising and falling potentials									Rising and falling potentials							
	t_D	t_L	Δt	% Δt	t_D	t_L	Δt	% Δt		t_D	t_L	Δt	% Δt	t_D	t_L	Δt	% Δt
0.35 kV	5	0	5	100	4.5	0	4.5	100	0.35 kV	16	2	14	87.5	15.5	2	13.5	87.1
0.4	9	0	9	100	9	0	9	100	0.4	23	2	21	91.3	23	2	21	91.3
0.6	23	0	23	100	22	0	22	100	0.6	20	1	19	95	21	1	20	95.2
0.75	35	0	35	100	35	0	35	100	0.75	12	1	11	91.6	13	1	12	92.3
1	36	1	35	97	35.5	1	34.5	97	1	6	2	4	66.6	6	2	4	66.6
1.5	21	2	19	90	21	2	19	90	1.5	8	3	5	62.5	8	3	5	62.5

(b) Temp. 23°. Observations taken after the ozoniser was given a slow temp. treat up to 100°.

0.35	3	0.35	4.4
0.4	6	0.4	11
0.6	18	0.6	38
0.75	25	0.75	63
1	40	1	124
1.5	82	1.5	

DISCUSSION

It was remarkable that aged ozoniser in use still showed "hysteresis" and hence it was quite certain that in the initial stages of the working of the ozoniser, the influence of ageing was found very prominent. Observations were taken after ageing the ozoniser for different intervals of time continuously. Observations for two such intervals are recorded (Table I). It is found that near V_m , the threshold potential, at which the gas breaks down as a dielectric, the % hysteresis is small but as the potential rises, it becomes prominent, e.g. at 0.4 kV, the Joshi effect for rising and falling potential was 85.6 and 73 (when the ozoniser was aged for 2 hours) and 94 and 90.9 (when the ozoniser was aged 4 hours), while at 0.55 kV, the corresponding effects were 75 and 60.4, and 77 and 66. When the ozoniser was aged for continuously 8 hours and observations recorded (Table I), the observations for rising and falling potentials agreed to a surprising accuracy.

The observations were repeated using IN 34 germanium crystal diode. This attempt was taken up with a view to studying if the reported hysteresis was associated with the A. C. detectors. Table III shows the results of such operations. The observations for rising and falling potentials tolerably agree. These sets were repeated with various values of chokes and at various temperatures and all the observations led to the same kind of result.

According to Joshi's mechanism of the effect, the formation of adsorption layer on the walls of the ozoniser is fundamental to the production of the effect. The adsorption layer explains clearly the "ageing" effect and its deactivation or derangement may lead to the reported hysteresis. Hence, observations were recorded (Table II) after resting the ozoniser for sufficiently long periods after ageing. If during the "rest period" there is any deformation of this layer, it would be evident from the observations. It is interesting to note that i_b , i_L , and Δi are widely different for rising and falling potentials, though % Δi is not sensibly affected. Studying the influence of ageing on Joshi effect in a freshly prepared ozoniser containing hydrogen (Vishwanathan, this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 199), it has been observed that moderate period of rest after ageing improves the %Joshi effect, while very large intervals, extending to days, exert a deteriorating influence. This kind of behaviour is explainable only on the postulate of "A variable adsorption-like boundary layer" postulated by Joshi (*Cur. Sci.*, 1945, 14, 175) and which is the main seat of the phenomenon of Joshi effect. These variations occur in a freshly prepared ozoniser, but if the ozoniser is aged, as is the present one under investigation, the time variation of the effect is negligible, as has been observed by Deo in chlorine (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1945, 21A, 76) and by the author in iodine vapour.

On account of the fact that the life of an atom in an excited state is very small ($T \cong 10^{-7}$ sec.), it is quite normal to expect (for low frequencies of A. C. potential) that the number of atoms in the excited states, whether the potential is increased from a lower value or decreased from a higher, should be practically identical. Hence, it is difficult to understand the occurrence of "hysteresis" on Joshi's theory which contemplates three stages viz., (1) formation of an adsorption-like boundary layer on the electrode surface under the applied field, (2) photo-electric emission from this layer under irradiation, and (3) the capture of photo-electrons by the excited atoms and molecules to form slow moving negative ions and produce the observed photo-dimensions Δi as a space-charge effect, unless some derangement or deactivation of the adsorption layer occurs affecting the electronic emission on exposure. The observations clearly show that if the boundary layer is properly set by continual ageing, the apparent hysteresis disappears. If the ozoniser is left to itself, the layer deactivates but soon sets if the ozoniser is aged one and the hysteresis disappears.

The frequency of A. C. supply may complicate the effect as it approaches the life of an atom in the excited state. It has been established that the Joshi effect decreases with increase in frequency and ultimately vanishes at radio frequencies. The experiments of Webb and Messenger (*Phys. Rev.*, 1929, 33, 319) on the reduction of the photo-electric current, as the frequency of A. C. voltage is varied from or below 60 cycles (zero frequencies) to about 10^7 cycles per sec. (radio frequency), may help to explain the cause of the absence of Joshi effect at very high frequencies.

Hundreds of sets taken in these laboratories showed the anomalous behaviour of i_b , with exciting potential i_0 rising to a maximum then gradually diminishing and then continuously rising. Looking to the observations of Deshmukh (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1949, 24A, 243) the author finds that similar behaviour of i_b has been observed by

him also, but it appears to have been lost sight of. Studying the effect of temperature on the production of Joshi effect, it is striking that at higher temperatures, the anomalous behaviour of i_b disappears, i. e. now the current i_b rises with exciting potential continuously. This result becomes still more illuminating, if the observations are repeated after slowly cooling the ozoniser at the room temperature. Here the usual behaviour of i_b with potentials is found. It is therefore suggested that proper ageing of heavier gases like Br_2 , I_2 is never complete though they may be in use for a pretty long time, and hence, a "hysteresis effect", which is in fact the "ageing effect", will normally be observed. Incidentally it appears that a better method of ageing an ozoniser will be to give it a slow temperature treat raising its temperature slowly and bringing it back to room temperature continuously passing the discharge during the operation. This method will very soon eliminate any ageing complications and will show results which can be relied upon.

The author's grateful thanks are due to Dr. S. S. Joshi, D. Sc., F. N. I. and Dr. W. V. Bhagwat, D. Sc., for keen interest during the course of the investigations.

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Received July 18, 1950.